

CAV 2026 Artifact

Paper title: Precise Verification of Transformers through ReLU-Catalyzed Abstraction Refinement

Claimed badges: Available + Reusable, once the final artifact package is uploaded to a DOI-backed archive. Reusable subsumes Functional in the CAV badge taxonomy. If a DOI is not available at submission time, request Functional.

Justification for the badges:

- Functional: the artifact contains the verifier implementation, trained compact checkpoints, datasets used by the compact artifact run, and scripts for reproducing the main experimental workflow: clean accuracy, baseline CrownBaF, r-BuFFeT, o-BuFFeT, timing records, and margin-vs-step plots.
- Reusable: the source code is included, the command-line interfaces are documented, the Docker image contains all Python dependencies and data needed for the bundled runs, and the scripts can be applied to newly trained checkpoints or additional verification instances.

Requirements:

- Architecture: x86_64.
- Docker: tested with Docker plus the NVIDIA Container Toolkit for GPU runs.
- Dependency manager: the Docker image is built with `uv` from `uv.lock`. The container creates and uses `/artifact/.venv`, matching the repository-local `.venv` workflow used outside Docker.
- GPU: strongly recommended. The artifact can run a reduced CPU smoke test, but the compact review, margin probes, and training-from-scratch workflows are intended for a CUDA-capable NVIDIA GPU.
- CPU: supported for basic smoke validation by omitting `--gpus all` and using `--cpu` where needed. CPU execution is much slower and is not recommended for judging optimization-heavy results.
- RAM: at least 16 GB for the smoke test; 32 GB or more recommended for the full compact review.
- Disk: about 20 GB free space for loading the Docker image and writing results.
- Time, smoke test: about 10-30 minutes on a recent NVIDIA GPU.
- Time, compact full review: about 2-6 hours on a recent NVIDIA GPU. CPU runs can be much slower.
- Time, training compact checkpoints from scratch: several hours to more than a day depending on hardware.
- External connectivity during evaluation: no. Internet access is only needed if rebuilding the Docker image from the Dockerfile instead of loading the provided `image.tar.gz`.

Validation snapshot:

- Date: 2026-04-27.
- Host: Docker 29.4.1 on x86_64 Linux with NVIDIA GeForce RTX 5080.
- Docker GPU runtime: `docker info` listed the `nvidia` runtime, and `docker run --gpus all buffet-cav26-ae:latest python -c "import torch; ..."` reported `torch==2.10.0+cu128`, CUDA available, and the RTX 5080 device.
- Quick Docker smoke command:

```
docker run --gpus all --rm \
-v "$PWD/results":/artifact/results \
--shm-size=8g \
-e ALPHA_OPT_STEPS=1 \
-e MARGIN_STEPS=3 \
buffet-cav26-ae:latest \
bash artifact/scripts/run-smoke.sh \
--output_dir results/docker_gpu_smoke_minimal \
--timeout 900
```

The quick run finished with `"ok": true`, clean accuracy `0.912`, and verified epsilon `0.32` for CrownBaF, r-BuFFeT, and o-BuFFeT on the one-sample smoke instance. Its margin probe improved from baseline margin `0.4217` to best margin `0.4519`.

Summary

This artifact package is used to reproduce representative experimental results for the paper "Precise Verification of Transformers through ReLU-Catalyzed Abstraction Refinement".

The paper studies robustness verification for Transformer classifiers. The core technical contribution is BuFFeT, a ReLU-catalyzed refinement of dot-product linear relaxations in self-attention. The artifact implements:

- CrownBaF, the baseline verifier;
- r-BuFFeT, the rule-based alpha selection strategy;
- o-BuFFeT, the optimization-based alpha refinement strategy;
- scripts to evaluate clean accuracy, verified radii, optimization margin curves, and training workflows.

Important model-scope note: the Docker image contains pre-trained compact smoke checkpoints with hidden size 64, intermediate size 128, and 4 attention heads. These are not the paper-table checkpoints used for the final experimental numbers. The smoke and full-review commands use the bundled checkpoints directly; they do not retrain models. The compact setting is included so CAV reviewers can validate the implementation, scripts, and qualitative trends in a reasonable amount of time. To run the paper code path from the beginning, train from scratch with the larger paper-scale configuration and then rerun the same verification commands.

Which Experiments Are Included?

The paper contains three main types of experiments.

- RQ1, verification precision: compare CrownBaF, r-BuFFeT, and o-BuFFeT in terms of maximal verified epsilon. In the artifact, this is reproduced by the compact sweep over Yelp and SST checkpoints with 1, 2, 3, and 6 layers.
- RQ2, optimization behavior: show how the margin changes during the optimization process of o-BuFFeT. In the artifact, this is reproduced by the margin probe and by the generated `margin_curve.png` plots.
- RQ3, efficiency: record the execution time of CrownBaF, r-BuFFeT, and o-BuFFeT. In the artifact, each result JSON and manifest records elapsed times. Absolute timing values are hardware-dependent.

The artifact also includes clean-accuracy evaluation and optional training commands. Training from scratch is provided as a separate workflow because it is substantially more expensive.

Preparation

Host GPU and Docker Setup

If the host already has Docker and `docker run --gpus all ...` works, skip this subsection and load the provided image. Otherwise, use the following Ubuntu oriented checklist. For other Linux distributions, follow the official pages linked here because package names can differ.

1. Install the NVIDIA driver on the host, not inside this artifact container. On Ubuntu, the recommended command-line path is:

```
sudo ubuntu-drivers list --gpgpu
sudo ubuntu-drivers install --gpgpu
sudo reboot
nvidia-smi
```

The last command should show the GPU name, driver version, and CUDA runtime compatibility. See Ubuntu's NVIDIA driver guide: <https://ubuntu.com/server/docs/how-to/graphics/install-nvidia-drivers/>

2. Install Docker Engine. On Ubuntu, Docker recommends installing from its apt repository:

```
sudo apt update
sudo apt install ca-certificates curl
sudo install -m 0755 -d /etc/apt/keyrings
sudo curl -fsSL https://download.docker.com/linux/ubuntu/gpg \
-o /etc/apt/keyrings/docker.asc
sudo chmod a+r /etc/apt/keyrings/docker.asc
sudo tee /etc/apt/sources.list.d/docker.sources <<EOF
Types: deb
URIs: https://download.docker.com/linux/ubuntu
Suites: $(. /etc/os-release && echo "${UBUNTU_CODENAME:-$VERSION_CODENAME}")
Components: stable
Architectures: $(dpkg --print-architecture)
Signed-By: /etc/apt/keyrings/docker.asc
EOF
sudo apt update
sudo apt install docker-ce docker-ce-cli containerd.io \
```

```
docker-buildx-plugin docker-compose-plugin
sudo docker run hello-world
```

See Docker's Ubuntu installation guide: <https://docs.docker.com/engine/install/ubuntu/>

3. Install NVIDIA Container Toolkit so Docker can pass the GPU into containers:

```
sudo apt-get update && sudo apt-get install -y --no-install-recommends \
ca-certificates curl gnupg2
curl -fsSL https://nvidia.github.io/libnvidia-container/gpgkey | \
sudo gpg --dearmor -o /usr/share/keyrings/nvidia-container-toolkit-keyring.gpg
curl -s -L https://nvidia.github.io/libnvidia-container/stable/deb/nvidia-container-toolkit.list | \
sed 's#deb https://#deb [signed-by=/usr/share/keyrings/nvidia-container-toolkit-keyring.gpg] https://#g' | \
sudo tee /etc/apt/sources.list.d/nvidia-container-toolkit.list
sudo apt-get update
sudo apt-get install -y nvidia-container-toolkit
sudo nvidia-ctl runtime configure --runtime=docker
sudo systemctl restart docker
```

See NVIDIA's Container Toolkit guide: <https://docs.nvidia.com/datacenter/cloud-native/container-toolkit/latest/install-guide.html>

4. Verify Docker GPU access:

```
docker info | grep -i nvidia || true
docker run --rm --gpus all ubuntu nvidia-smi
```

If `nvidia-smi` works on the host but the Docker command fails, the problem is in the host Docker/NVIDIA Container Toolkit configuration, not in this artifact image.

Load and Enter the Artifact Image

Load the Docker image:

```
docker load < image.tar.gz
```

Run the Docker container with GPU support:

```
mkdir -p results
docker run --gpus all --rm -it \
-v "$PWD/results":/artifact/results \
--shm-size=8g \
buffet-cav26-ae:latest
```

The `-v` option stores generated reports and figures in your local `results/` directory. The `--rm` option makes the container disposable, and `--shm-size=8g` gives PyTorch enough shared memory for the compact runs. If the machine has no NVIDIA GPU, omit `--gpus all`; the smoke test will automatically fall back to a reduced CPU mode.

If `docker run --gpus all` fails even though `nvidia-smi` works on the host, the host Docker installation is missing the NVIDIA container runtime. Install and register NVIDIA Container Toolkit on the host, restart Docker, and confirm that `docker info` lists an NVIDIA runtime before rerunning the command.

Inside the container, all commands below should be run from:

```
cd /artifact
```

The Docker image uses `uv` during build and contains a ready-to-use repository-local virtual environment at `/artifact/.venv`. The image profile puts `/artifact/.venv/bin` on `PATH`, so `python ...` uses the same environment as `.venv/bin/python ...`.

Smoke Test

Run:

```
artifact/scripts/run-smoke.sh
```

The script writes a timestamped report under `results/cav_ae_smoke/`. It checks:

- Python, PyTorch, CUDA, and git/environment information;
- syntax/import health for the verifier entry points;
- clean accuracy on one compact checkpoint;
- one-sample verification for CrownBaF, r-BuFFeT, and o-BuFFeT;
- a short margin-optimization probe when CUDA is available.

Expected behavior:

- The script should finish without errors.
- The console should show live progress instead of staying silent. Verification prints the sample index, token or token pair, bracket expansion/shrinkage, and each binary-search radius with the current safe/unsafe result.
- The final printed JSON should contain "ok": true.
- The verification section should contain entries for `baseline`, `r_buffer`, and `o_buffer`.
- If CUDA is available, the margin probe should show that o-BuFFeT matches or improves the non-optimized margin on the selected compact example.

Full Review: Compact Reproduction

Run:

```
artifact/scripts/run-full-review.sh
```

This command runs the compact artifact sweep:

- datasets: Yelp and SST;
- layers: 1, 2, 3, and 6;
- perturbation: one word, L1 norm;
- methods: CrownBaF, r-BuFFeT, and o-BuFFeT;
- five verification samples per model;
- short margin probes for Figure-6-style behavior.

Outputs are written to `results/cav_full_review/<timestamp>/`. The most useful files are:

- `manifest.json`: all commands, return codes, timing, summaries, and failures;
- `commands.txt`: exact commands used;
- `accuracy.json`: clean accuracy for the bundled compact checkpoints;
- `verification/*/res.json`: verified epsilon values for each model/method;
- `margin/*/summary.json` and `margin/*/margin_curve.png`: margin-vs-step results.

Expected qualitative results:

- r-BuFFeT should be at least competitive with CrownBaF on the bundled compact checkpoints.
- o-BuFFeT should match or improve r-BuFFeT on the margin probes, while taking longer because it performs iterative alpha optimization.
- The most important diagnostic for RQ2 is the `margin_curve.png` trend. Our method is optimization-based, so exact values are affected by the optimizer, learning rate, learning-rate schedule, number of alpha-optimization steps, number of binary-search iterations, random seed, and hardware. If the margin curve follows the RQ2 phenomenon, namely the optimized margin improves over the initial/non-optimized bound or at least converges to a comparable value on the compact instance, the artifact run should be considered successful. The remaining gap to paper-table numbers is mainly the expensive work of training paper-scale models and tuning the optimization budget.
- Exact epsilon and timing values may differ from the paper because the bundled checkpoints are compact smoke models rather than the paper-scale experimental checkpoints.

For a shorter full-review pass, reviewers may reduce the sample budget:

```
SAMPLES=2 ALPHA_OPT_STEPS=10 artifact/scripts/run-full-review.sh
```

Training Workflows

The artifact can start from training.

By default, the CAV Docker image already includes compact smoke checkpoints. They are useful for checking the artifact quickly, but they are not the models used to produce the paper tables. Reviewers who want to start from the complete training pipeline can train from scratch and then reuse the same verification scripts.

For a quick training sanity check, run:

```
artifact/scripts/run-training-smoke.sh
```

This trains a one-layer compact SST model for one epoch on a reduced training split and writes the checkpoint under `results/cav_training_smoke/`. Training prints each batch by default through `--display_interval 1`; increase `DISPLAY_INTERVAL` or pass `--display_interval N` if less frequent progress is preferred.

To train all compact checkpoints used by the artifact, run:

```
script/train_compact.sh
```

This trains Yelp and SST compact models for layers 1, 2, 3, 4, and 6. It can take many hours depending on the GPU. After training, evaluate clean accuracy:

```
python eval_accuracy.py --layers 1 2 3 4 6
```

Then rerun:

```
artifact/scripts/run-full-review.sh
```

To train paper-scale standard Transformer checkpoints, use the same `main.py` interface but set the paper configuration, for example:

```
python main.py \  
  --train \  
  --data yelp \  
  --dir ./verified_models/model_yelp_3_paper_scale \  
  --num_layers 3 \  
  --hidden_size 512 \  
  --intermediate_size 512 \  
  --num_attention_heads 8
```

Paper-scale training and full verification are substantially more expensive. The compact Docker artifact is therefore the recommended CAV review workflow.

Reproduce Individual Results

Baseline:

```
python run_bounds.py --data yelp \  
  --model ./verified_models/model_yelp_1 \  
  --method baf --p 1 --samples 10
```

r-BuFFeT:

```
python run_bounds.py --data yelp \  
  --model ./verified_models/model_yelp_1 \  
  --method baf --p 1 --samples 10 \  
  --double_z --k 1 --suffix r_buffer
```

o-BuFFeT:

```
python run_bounds.py --data yelp \  
  --model ./verified_models/model_yelp_1 \  
  --method baf --p 1 --samples 10 \  
  --double_z --alpha_opt --alpha_opt_steps 100 --k 1 --suffix o_buffer
```

Margin curve:

```
python experiments/fig6_margin_curve.py \  
  --data yelp \  
  --model_dir ./verified_models/model_yelp_3 \  
  --p 1 \  
  --example_index 60 \  
  --token_pos 2 \  
  --eps 0.3 \  
  --max_steps 120
```

```
--max_verify_length 8 \  
--alpha_lr 0.01 \  
--init_mode random
```

The generated `margin_curve.png` should show the margin over optimization steps, together with the baseline reference line.

Command Parameters

Docker options used above:

- `--gpus all`: exposes all host NVIDIA GPUs to the container. Omit it for CPU mode.
- `--rm`: removes the container after it exits.
- `-it`: opens an interactive terminal, useful for manual inspection.
- `-v "$PWD/results":/artifact/results`: writes container outputs into the host `results/` directory.
- `--shm-size=8g`: increases Docker shared memory for PyTorch workloads.
- `-e NAME=value`: overrides script defaults, for example `-e ALPHA_OPT_STEPS=10`.

`artifact/scripts/run-smoke.sh`:

- `ALPHA_OPT_STEPS`: number of optimization steps used by o-BuFFeT in the smoke verification; default 5.
- `MARGIN_STEPS`: number of optimization steps in the margin-curve probe; default 10.
- `OUTPUT_ROOT`: parent directory for timestamped smoke outputs; default `results/cav_ae_smoke`.
- `--output_dir DIR`: write this run to an exact output directory instead of a timestamped one.
- `--timeout SECONDS`: per-subcommand timeout; default 900.
- `--cpu`: force CPU execution.
- `--skip_margin`: skip the margin probe, useful for CPU-only machines.

`artifact/scripts/run-full-review.sh`:

- `SAMPLES`: number of verification samples per model/method; default 5.
- `NUM_VERIFY_ITERS`: binary-search iterations for each certified radius; default 3 in the compact review.
- `ALPHA_OPT_STEPS`: o-BuFFeT alpha-optimization steps; default 20.
- `OUTPUT_ROOT`: parent directory for full-review outputs; default `results/cav_full_review`.
- Additional arguments are passed to `experiments/reproduce_all_5.py`; useful examples are `--dry_run`, `--cpu`, `--timeout SECONDS`, `--layers 1 3 6`, `--datasets yelp sst`, and `--no_progress`.

Verification parameters in `main.py` and `run_bounds.py`:

- `--verify`: run certification rather than training or clean accuracy.
- `--dir / --model`: checkpoint directory.
- `--data`: dataset name, usually `yelp` or `sst` for this artifact.
- `--method baf`: use the CrownBaF/BuFFeT verifier implementation.
- `--p`: perturbation norm; the compact review mainly uses $p=1$.
- `--perturbed_words`: certify one word or two words; supported values are 1 and 2.
- `--samples`: number of correctly classified validation/test examples to verify.
- `--max_verify_length`: skip longer examples to keep verification practical.
- `--max_eps`: initial radius used to search for a valid verification bracket.
- `--num_verify_iters`: binary-search refinement steps. Larger values give a more precise radius but cost more time.
- `--double_z`: enable r-BuFFeT's ReLU-catalyzed refinement.
- `--alpha_opt`: enable o-BuFFeT's optimization-based alpha refinement.
- `--alpha_opt_steps`: number of optimizer steps per radius check in o-BuFFeT.
- `--k`: rule-based alpha threshold used by r-BuFFeT.
- `--log` and `--res`: text log path and JSON result path.
- `--display_interval`: training batch logging interval; default 1.
- `--progress_interval`: verification binary-search logging interval; default 1, meaning every step is printed.
- `--cpu`: force CPU execution even if CUDA is visible.

Training parameters in `main.py`:

- `--train`: train a checkpoint from scratch.
- `--num_layers`, `--hidden_size`, `--intermediate_size`, and `--num_attention_heads`: Transformer size. The bundled smoke models use 1/2/3/4/6 layers, hidden size 64, intermediate size 128, and 4 attention heads; paper-scale examples use larger settings such as hidden size 512 and 8 heads.

- `--num_epochs`: number of training epochs. The name is kept for compatibility with the original code.
- `--batch_size`: training batch size.
- `--lr`: learning rate.
- `--small`: use the reduced dataset path for compact experiments.

Margin-curve parameters in `experiments/fig6_margin_curve.py`:

- `--model_dir`, `--data`, `--p`: model, dataset, and norm used by the probe.
- `--example_index` and `--token_pos`: fixed example and token whose margin is plotted.
- `--eps`: perturbation radius for the margin probe.
- `--max_steps`: optimization steps shown in the curve.
- `--alpha_lr`: alpha optimizer learning rate.
- `--init_mode`: alpha initialization, one of warm, random, or zero.
- `--output_root`: parent directory for the generated `summary.json`, `margin_curve.csv`, and `margin_curve.png`.

Criteria for Reproducibility

Clean accuracy on bundled compact checkpoints should be close to:

Layers	Yelp	SST
1	0.912	0.826
2	0.912	0.832
3	0.913	0.823
6	0.914	0.831

For verification precision, exact numeric epsilon values depend on hardware, random sample selection, and optimization budget. The expected trend is that r-BuFFeT and o-BuFFeT are competitive with, and often improve over, CrownBaF.

For margin optimization, reviewers should primarily inspect the generated margin-vs-step plots. Because o-BuFFeT solves an optimization problem, the final margin depends on choices such as optimizer, learning rate, learning-rate schedule, optimization steps, binary-search iterations, seed, and selected example. A successful compact artifact run should show the RQ2 qualitative behavior: the optimized margin improves during the process or at least matches the non-optimized reference on the selected instance. Reproducing the exact paper-table values requires the larger models and substantially more training and tuning time.

For timing, the exact values should not be compared literally with the paper. The expected trend is that r-BuFFeT is close to CrownBaF, while o-BuFFeT takes longer because it performs iterative alpha optimization.

Usage for New Problem Instances

To verify a new trained checkpoint, place it under `verified_models/` with the same checkpoint layout used by the bundled models, then run:

```
python main.py --verify \
  --dir ./verified_models/YOUR_MODEL \
  --data yelp \
  --method baf \
  --p 1 \
  --perturbed_words 1 \
  --samples 10 \
  --double_z \
  --alpha_opt
```

To change the dataset, add files under `data/<dataset>/` and extend `data_utils.py` if the input format differs from Yelp/SST. To change model size, use the training flags in `Parser.py`, such as `--num_layers`, `--hidden_size`, `--intermediate_size`, and `--num_attention_heads`.

Docker Image Layout

```
.
├─ artifact
```

```

|   ├── README.md
|   └── scripts
|       ├── run-full-review.sh
|       ├── run-smoke.sh
|       └── run-training-smoke.sh
├── experiments
|   ├── ae_smoke.py
|   ├── fig6_margin_curve.py
|   └── reproduce_all_5.py
├── Models
├── Verifiers
├── data
|   ├── model_base
|   ├── sst
|   └── yelp
├── script
|   ├── reproduce_all_5.sh
|   └── train_compact.sh
├── verified_models
|   ├── model_sst_{1,2,3,4,6}
|   └── model_yelp_{1,2,3,4,6}
├── .venv
├── main.py
├── run_bounds.py
├── eval_accuracy.py
├── pyproject.toml
└── uv.lock

```

The image intentionally omits source-tree maintenance notes, paper PDFs, generated result directories, old figures, ACC/tabular data, TensorBoard logs, and legacy duplicate checkpoints. The submitted zip outside the image contains only `image.tar.gz`, this README, LICENSE, and SHA256SUMS.